

IRISCC

D2.3

Report of user requirement for Regional Scale SDLs and knowledge service provision

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Abstract

Key words

Service design lab, pilot, land-use, desertification, climate change

Deliverable 2.3 presents the implementation of IRISCC Service Design Labs (SDLs) as a co-design approach for developing transdisciplinary Knowledge Services addressing climate-related risks. SDLs bring together research infrastructure communities from the environmental, health, and social sciences with policy, industry, and civil society actors to co-create solutions with high relevance and implementation potential.

Service Design Lab #1 (SDL#1) strengthens science-practice collaboration within the Eisenwurzen LTSER platform by co-designing a stakeholder-driven framework for assessing land-use vulnerability to climate change. The Lab highlights the central role of land users within interconnected stakeholder networks and identifies key conditions for effective collaboration, including early engagement, high-quality participatory processes, and sustained communication.

Service Design Lab #2 (SDL#2) supports the Region of Crete in addressing drought, land degradation, and desertification through a participatory, science-informed process across the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem Nexus. The Lab integrates scientific evidence and local knowledge to co-design feasible, scalable, and transferable solutions with relevance for other Mediterranean regions.

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Terminology / Acronyms	
Term/Acronym	Definition
SDL	Service Design Lab
RI	Research Infrastructure
WEFE	Water-Ecosystem-Food-Energy
NGO	Non-governmental Organization
eLTSER	Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, Critical Zone and Socioecological Research
CAP	Common Agriculture Policy
ÖBF	Österreichische Bundesforste
IUCN Cat. II	National Park Category
OAK	Crete Development Organization
TEE/TAK	Technical Chamber of Greece
EYDE	Special Management and Implementation Service of the Ministry of Interior
BOAK	Northern Road AxisFF
LTSER	Long-term Socio-ecological Research

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Executive summary

Deliverable 2.3 focuses on implementing co-design activities through the innovative concept of Service Design Labs (SDLs) to jointly develop transdisciplinary Knowledge Services. The purpose of SDLs is to develop Knowledge Services to address targeted challenges concerning climate risks and mitigation. The goal is to provide the opportunity for experts and stakeholders to co-create a solution to reduce climate risks, increasing the probability of implementation of recommended measures. SDLs will bring together research infrastructure (RI) communities from the environmental, health, and social sciences with users and stakeholders representing regulators, industry, and civil society.

SDL#1 focuses on strengthening science–practice collaboration in the Eisenwurzen LTSER platform through the co-design of a stakeholder-driven framework for assessing land-use vulnerability to climate change. Building on comprehensive stakeholder mapping, expert interviews, social network analysis, and a regional stakeholder workshop, SDL#1 addresses the diverse land-use system of the region, encompassing agriculture, forestry, conservation, regional development, and policy actors. The identification of land users as the most central stakeholder group, embedded within complex communication and influence networks involving extension services, protected areas, regional development initiatives, and public authorities. The SDL highlights that effective collaboration depends on relationships built on equal terms, high-quality participatory processes, early and meaningful stakeholder involvement, and sustained communication beyond individual project lifecycles. Stakeholders consistently emphasised the need for tangible regional benefits, practical and accessible research outputs, and clearer feedback loops between research and practice.

SDL#2 supports the Region of Crete in addressing drought, land degradation, and increasing desertification risks in the Messara Plain and the Asterousia Mountains through a participatory, science-informed co-design process. Building on the AQUAMAN stakeholder consultation framework, SDL#2 brings together regional authorities, research institutions, local governments, farmers, livestock breeders, water utilities, Non-governmental Organisations (NGOs), and UNESCO-related actors to work across the Water–Energy–Food–Ecosystem (WEFE) Nexus. The Lab aims to deliver a strategic regional plan while testing a transferable methodology that links scientific knowledge, policy objectives, and local implementation, with the Asterousia UNESCO Biosphere Reserve. The SDL synthesizes long-term ecological data, regional statistics, and stakeholder knowledge to identify the main drivers of desertification, including groundwater overexploitation, inefficient irrigation, soil fertility decline, biodiversity loss, unsustainable grazing, and governance and policy constraints. A key insight is that desertification is driven not only by climate change but also by long-standing land-use practices and socio-institutional factors]. The co-design process highlights the value of agro-ecological and nature-based solutions that improve water efficiency, restore soils, and enhance ecosystem services, while remaining feasible for local practitioners.

Future actions will prioritize implementing the co-designed program of measures, focusing on efficient irrigation, soil carbon restoration, sustainable grazing management, and policy

alignment, particularly within Common Agriculture Policy (CAP) frameworks. Pilot demonstrations, continued stakeholder engagement, and capacity-building activities are essential to build trust and support uptake. The SDL#2 approach is designed to be scalable and transferable to other Mediterranean regions facing similar climate and land degradation challenges. SDL#2 proposes a socio-techno-ecological methodology for strategic planning to address desertification that can be used as a model for RI services.

1 Introduction

Deliverable 2.3 focuses on implementing co-design activities through the innovative concept of SDLs to jointly develop transdisciplinary Knowledge Services. The purpose of SDLs is to develop Knowledge Services to address targeted challenges concerning climate risk. The goal is to provide the opportunity for experts and stakeholders to co-create a solution, increasing the probability of implementation. SDLs will bring together RI communities from the environmental, health, and social sciences with users and stakeholders representing regulators, industry, and civil society. The co-design process involves the early stages of service development, including defining the purpose and design of the service, engaging users and stakeholders to identify their needs and requirements, determining the necessary informational inputs such as data, computing, and models from RIs and other sources, and specifying the expected outputs in terms of format and timeframe [R1].

Over the course of the project, four SDLs will be established: two at the local and regional level and two at the European level. Each SDL will assign clear roles, including the driver or owner of the service, who will present it to the Infrastructure Board, as well as users, stakeholders, developers, data providers, and hosts to ensure the sustainability of the co-created services. At the local and regional level, IRISCC will use two eLTSEr (Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, Critical Zone and Socioecological Research) Platforms that reflect different climate change impacts and vulnerabilities: the Eisenwurzen Platform in Austria (LAND USE DECISION MAKING SDL-SDL #1) and the Messara-Asterousia Mountains in Crete, Greece (EVALUATION OF ADAPTATION AND MITIGATION ACTIONS TO DROUGHT SDL-SDL #2). At the European level, one SDL will examine the effects of climate change on soil carbon sequestration and carbon storage, supporting the evaluation of carbon credits and carbon trading (SOIL CARBON SDL-SDL #3), while another will focus on user-defined services that support European climate policies through the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S, Copernicus Co-design lab on climate services SDL-SDL #4).

The Knowledge Services to be delivered by the RIs and implemented in WP5 are in the development process.

This report describes the details of SDL#1 and SDL#2 that deal with service development at the regional level. A separate report D2.2. describes the continental level service development of SDL#3 and SDL#4. In parts 2.1 and 3.1 each SDL will explain their stakeholder mapping process. Following in parts 2.2 and 3.2, the co-design activities will be established. Parts 2.3 and 3.3 will list the user needs and requirements. In parts 2.4, 3.4 and 2.5, 3.5 the informational input will be defined and the output respectively.

2 Land-Use Decision-Making

Service Design Lab, SDL #1

2.1 Stakeholder Mapping

In 2023, as part of the eLTER PLUS project BOKU conducted a comprehensive stakeholder analysis based on expert interviews and a land user network analysis. Content analysis of the expert interviews allowed us to identify 142 land-use stakeholders and stakeholder groups across the whole land-use sector in the Eisenwurzen region. Due to the nature of the open-ended questions and ensuing discussions during the interviews, respondents equally referred to broad stakeholder groups (such as landowners or processing industry) as well as to very individual stakeholders (such as naming specific landowners or retail businesses).

The most central stakeholder group are the land-users themselves. Respondents identified several sector-specific sub-groups of land users and used certain characteristics to differentiate this relatively broad group. The characteristic most often referred to relates to the area extent owned or managed by a land user. In the agricultural sector these were small-scale family-run businesses, small- and medium-sized farms and large landowners. Large landowners were often identified as either being aristocratic families or the Admont Monastery, one of the largest private landowners in the region. A second characteristic that was used to differentiate land users was their mode of operation in terms of full-time or part-time. This differentiation is important because many family-run businesses cannot be sustained by the agricultural practice alone but require additional income from other, often non-farming occupations. In addition, one relevant sub-group are farms that simultaneously operate a tourism business typically called 'holiday farm', which is a common diversification strategy in the region to generate additional on-farm income. Another sub-group, which was explicitly mentioned, are 'newcomers' to the farming sector. In the forestry sector, size was the most important criterion for differentiation. Corresponding to the regions forest property structure, most forest owners identified are large landowners. These are, on the one hand, public owners such as the Federal Forests Austria (ÖBF), state forests owned by the Austrian provinces such as the Styrian State Forests as well as the City of Vienna. Most of the protected areas in the region, such as the National Park Kalkalpen, the National Park Gesäuse (both IUCN Cat. II) and the Wilderness Area Dürrenstein-Lassingtal (IUCN Cat. Ia/Ib) belong to these public owners. Small-scale forest owners were often referred to as mixed forest-farms, a characteristic that is valid for many small and medium sized farms across Austria. Another group of small-scale forest owners were identified as so-called 'remote' or 'urban' forest owners who are characterized by the fact that they primarily own forests due to investment reasons without much interest or activity concerning the actual forest management. The forestry sector is additionally characterized by a number of land managers, who are not the owners themselves. This corresponds primarily to publicly owned land where official forest rangers and hunters play

an important role, and, additionally, the protected areas where certain management structures and advisory panels are in place.

Another important stakeholder group is that of extension and consulting services. The most relevant actor in this group is the chamber of agriculture, operating at the level of federal provinces as well as more locally with their regional subsidiaries called district chambers. The chamber of agriculture is responsible for both the agriculture and forestry sectors and it was by far the most often discussed stakeholder in the context of extension and consulting services. The main activities of the chamber of agriculture and its subsidiaries are, by law, the official representation of interests of and consultation to farmers and foresters. Relating to the agricultural sector, the only other relevant stakeholder in this group mentioned during the interviews was BIO-Austria, which is the official representation of interests and consulting organization for organic farming. This first categorization already shows that consulting and lobbying are closely tied to each other. When discussing the forestry sector, interviewees identified a number of additional stakeholders including on a public level the district forest inspections, district rangers and forest authorities, as well as private forestry consultants.

Due to the number and extent of protected areas in the region, the conservation sector plays an important role in the local land-use system and is connected to many different other stakeholder groups. As described above, the national parks and wilderness area have public landowners, while the nature parks stretch across cultural landscapes with multiple public and private landowners. Both categories have strictly defined conservation objectives and additionally engage in tourism, but nature parks also strive to protect and develop valuable cultural landscapes in connection with their land-use and management aspects. This approach encompasses not only conservation and recreational/touristic uses, but also focuses on regional and rural development including the creation of additional jobs in the land-use sector. Other important players in this regard are, on the one hand, regional development initiatives such as the LEADER regions or the National and Nature Park Partners, which also strive to support sustainable rural development, and, on the other hand, a range of conservation Non-governmental Organisations, NGOs, (i.e. the Austrian League for Nature Conservation, Friends of Nature Austria, World Wildlife Fund, Mollner Kreis) as well as the Natural Forest Network (which works with local stakeholders to implement connecting corridors between the protected areas) and LUKA (Arbeitskreis Luchs OÖ), a regional initiative for protection of the Lynx. Important actors in the field of politics and conservation are, besides the federal government, the three provincial governments and parliaments (Landtag and Landesregierung) including their environmental secretaries (Landesrat für Naturschutz), as well as the municipalities. Nature conservation in Austria is regulated by the nine Austrian federal provinces, resulting in nine distinct nature protection laws as well as distinct implementations of the EU Habitats Directive, the Water Framework Directive and the Bird Directive. As conservation objectives also create conflicts between different land users, there exist local initiatives to tackle important issues, for example the behaviour of certain tourist groups (e.g. mountain bikers) inside protected areas by the National Park Bike- and Hiking-Specialists. In the educational

sector, conservation actors are primarily the National and Nature Park Partner Schools and rangers.

Results from the social network analysis reveal insights about the land-use related communication between actors. We thereby required respondents to allocate their most important communication partners to a predefined set of stakeholder groups, specify their communication frequency with each partner (differentiated by a range of land-use related topics), as well as to assess the influence of this communication on the respondent's decision-making. Additionally, we collected a series of demographic and farm-related variables. Actor groups with the most diverse set of connections are small (< 50 ha) and large (> 50 ha) land users, protected areas, the chamber of agriculture and other public consultants. While the chamber of agriculture is not connected to a large number of different groups, it communicates with the largest number of individual small and large land users at a relatively high frequency. The data, for example, reveals that communication with the retail actor group has the highest average influence on small land users' decision-making. Furthermore, it shows that protected areas are highly influenced by its communication with the local population, large land users and the chamber of agriculture. Interestingly, many land users also replied that they not only receive but also provide relevant information to the chamber (which is not represented in the network graphs, at this stage).

2.2 Co-Design Service Lab with Region

This Service Lab focuses on developing a stakeholder-driven framework to assess the vulnerability of land to climate change (Figure 1). It will involve farmers, foresters, and regional developers in a comprehensive process to design a tool that considers both socio-economic and biophysical factors. The co-design process considers the requirements of the regional stakeholder groups for the SDL and their needs for productive collaboration with scientists. It takes into account stakeholders' experiences in earlier collaboration with scientific partners, what tools and measures worked well, and where they see difficulties in collaboration.

Interviewees were selected based on stakeholder mapping and snowball sampling and represented different stakeholders' groups from the case study region, mainly regional development, nature conservation and research. Interviews were conducted between March and October 2025 with actors from the case study region (8 male, 5 female). Out of 13 actors six represented regional development, five nature conservation, four research, one citizen science, politics, and intermediaries, some representing more than one sector. Interview duration was between 37 minutes and 1,5 hours.

The interview guideline was structured along five main themes. The preliminary questions posed sought to understand the **respondents' personal history** with the platform and their initial motivations for participating in projects or activities associated with it. The second thematic block explored the thematic **links between the platform activities and the stakeholder's field**, the core topics in their discipline, connections between those topics and

the LTSER (Long-term Socio-ecological Research) platform, if there was an evolution of thematic relevance over time (stable vs. emerging topics), what personal contributions to the platform and which concrete benefits the interviewee derived from participating (e.g. new ideas, networking, economic gains), as well as thematic gaps (topics that are insufficiently addressed by the platform). The third set of questions focused on the **personal network and relationships** within the platform. It asked for regular contacts and collaborations within the platform, perceptions of influential actors shaping platform activities, former participants and reasons for their disengagement, how the platform is perceived in the wider region (recognition, stakeholder awareness), also which platform elements the actors desired and which expectations they had from participation. The fourth theme that was explored concerned **project involvement** and the manner in which participation processes were conducted. The focus of the enquiry was on the participation in past projects and the manner in which said participation was organised. In addition, the interviews sought to understand which participatory methods had been employed, the quality of participation, and the evolution of participation since the foundation of the platform. Moreover, the fourth thematic block addressed the dynamics of communication, in addition to the question of which actor groups were strongly or underrepresented, and in which subject areas. It also addressed the importance of networking and exchange during participation. The fifth thematic part of the interview guideline focussed on the **transfer of results and impact** in the region. It asked for the significance of the practical impact of project outcomes for the stakeholders, for specific examples of results that have influenced the region (ecological, socioeconomic, networking), which results were useful to be implemented in their own work, and which were preferred formats for receiving and disseminating results (reports, briefs, workshops, etc.).

Following the interviews a stakeholder workshop was organised on November 24th, 2025, in the region. 22 people took part in the workshop, including 10 representatives from research and educational institutions, 7 representatives from nature reserves and national parks, 2 managers of “Klima- und Energiemodellregionen (Climate and Energy Model Region), one LEADER manager, one KLAR! Manager (climate change adaptation region) and one representative from a regional management organisation. The group also included individuals who had previously participated in interviews. The primary motivation for the focus on this stakeholder group was their position at an intermediary level between regional practitioners and science actors. The workshop focused on facilitating exchange between researchers and regional developers, and on a discussion of how the requirements of regional developers for productive collaboration with scientists could be realised. In addition, the opportunities for collaboration and the potential for such cooperation were explored. This discussion was organised around three main questions: “If the platform and regional development worked together perfectly, what would that look like? What are your expectations and wishes?”, “Which issues or challenges in your region could be supported by the platform or LTSER research – and how?”, and “What initial steps could we take together to seize these opportunities? Who could contribute what?”

The results of the interviews and workshop were then analysed using thematic analysis according to Braun and Clarke [R2]. This qualitative research approach emphasises the

active role of the researcher through the development of codes and themes. Subjectivity is inevitable in this approach. It is therefore important to constantly reflect on personal assumptions and practices in terms of how they can influence and limit the analysis.

Figure 1. Procedure and method of SDL Eisenwurzen.

2.3 User Requirements and Needs

2.3.1 Interviews

During the analysis of the interviews, three main themes were developed. They reflect different aspects of stakeholders' needs for the Service Design Lab and their perspectives on science-practice collaboration: (1) Relationship and collaboration between science and practice, (2) benefits and impact in the region, and (3) exchange within the LTSER platform

Relationship and collaboration between science and practice

The first main theme focusses on the relationship between science and practice in the LTSER platform Eisenwurzen and which factors support the science-practice collaboration.

Collaboration on equal terms is seen as an important factor. Stakeholders reflected on this theme from different perspectives. They said that, especially in the first time of the platforms' existence, the relationship to researchers was often one-sided: Stakeholders were asked to participate in specific phases of the research process (e.g. interviews, workshops) but received very little back. Research results stayed mainly in the academic field and were only partly fed back to practitioners. In contrast to that, there is a feeling that it is hard to get researchers to take up research questions from the region. However, they acknowledge that, particularly in the early years of the platform, the expectations of

practitioners towards science were unrealistic, and the research problems raised by practitioners were vague in their formulation. This is reflected in several responses:

“Well, I’ve always noticed that at the beginning, someone comes along and wants a lot of information.” (Interview 4)

And similarly: *“And what was simply a bit of criticism, I can also say now, was that we said, yes, it’s a bit for us, it has a bit of a one-way character, yes. Because the researchers always contacted us and asked if they could do something with us, (...) Reversely, however, it was often difficult when we said, we have a question for so-and-so, can’t you take that up, yes. I mean, our questions were perhaps often very vague.” (Interview 2)*

This one-sided aspect of the science–practice relationship also exists in reverse, when scientists are not seen as collaborative partners but as “fact suppliers” for practice e.g. carrying out material analysis or statistical analysis for very specific purposes.

Both researchers as well as practitioners wish for collaboration on an equal footing in which different ways of knowledge production are equally valued and respected. Based on past experiences of collaboration, they emphasize that this can lead to new opportunities for both sides and create a better connection between science and practice:

“The point I am trying to make is that we are not taking advantage of the opportunities that arise from the mutual understanding between so-called academic science and the craftsmanship of lay people.” (Interview 6)

“And I think that once you break down that barrier, that research on equal terms, that creates a better connection.” (Interview 3)

Another important enabler of science–practice collaboration is the quality and relevance of participatory processes. The main motivator for stakeholders to participate in research projects in the first place is personal interest in the research question or a specific practical challenge that the project addresses. For stakeholders to continue participating in the project, the participatory process must be of a consistently high quality. This includes professional facilitation but also simple practical manners like good hosting, such as catering and suitable spaces.

Another aspect is integrating the relevant actors as early as possible, but still at a point where their contribution is valuable. The time factor also needs to be considered when planning events and workshops. This means taking into account the realities of stakeholders’ lives.

“And so, with the population, it’s a matter of differentiation again. If I take farmers, for example, then I’m not allowed to do anything when they’re all going into the barn. That sounds silly now, but these are just little things that you still have to look out for.” (Interview 7)

Time constraints are a main factor when it comes to participatory research. In most situations, stakeholders are not compensated for the time they give to projects, in contrast to researchers or other professionals which can participate in their working hours. Some of the interviewees challenged this situation and asked for funding schemes to make this possible, in the hope that this will make it possible for more stakeholders to participate.

"... and the farmer, we assume that he does this in his spare time, right? And that's something I often notice, yes, that it's simply forgotten that the people we want to cooperate and work with, (...) um, that we have to pay them." (Interview 10)

Depending on the level of participation, a well-executed process will call for flexibility, both in the research process and the participation process. Integration of different forms of knowledge might challenge assumptions made by scientists when designing the research process and asking for adaptation of methods, research questions, or hypotheses.

"And that was quite good, because from then on, so to speak, another loop was made. (...) And then we were also invited to additional interviews, so to speak." (Interview 9)

Furthermore, effective communication is an essential prerequisite for a good collaboration between science and practice. Communication can serve as both an enabler and a hindrance. Communication with stakeholders happens mainly during projects and often stops almost completely after the end of a projects' lifetime. This frequently results in the aforementioned "one-way" scenario, wherein stakeholders find themselves unaware of the impact of their contributions on the one hand and on the other hand cannot make practical use of project results. Both of these aspects are relevant for successful science-practice collaboration. Firstly, it is vital to recognize that stakeholders will be motivated to participate in such collaborative endeavors if they can discern the purpose of their involvement. Secondly, the implementation of scientific findings in their practical work constitutes a primary motivation for their participation. If communication is taken seriously, it is time-consuming and ideally carried on after funded research projects come to their end.

"But at some point, the project ends and then there is actually no follow-up work or follow-up support, or even the step where you say, yes, now we have results, now we could perhaps put them into practice or bring them closer to reality." (Interview 5)

Benefits and impact in the region

Actors both from science and practice emphasize the importance of creating benefits for the region through research projects. This is regarded by many as a prerequisite for participation in the first place, and past experience of participating in projects or activities that, in their view, did not create any benefit or impact has led to some of them dropping out of the LTSER platform's activities [R3].

"For us, it wasn't really something that provided much inspiration in terms of topics or anything like that. (Interview 8)"

Nevertheless, what counts as a benefit or impact depends on the perspective of the individual stakeholder. For some, awareness raising on socio-ecological challenges, or a new thought, an impulse, that leads to a small change in perspective is already of significant value, while others expect specific recommendations or instructions, such as guidelines. Also, impact can arise from being challenged by research results and getting the possibility to discuss possible scenarios for the region's future development with researchers. In addition, the LTSER platform Eisenwurzen has a long-standing history of participative research, which has resulted in some stakeholders experiencing difficulties in discerning which activities generated which impacts.

"So, it has so many diffuse, elusive benefits." (Interview 11)

"I couldn't say right now, no, I can't think of any specific examples that have really changed my work in a fundamental way, or where I always learn something essential. Nevertheless, there are many small aspects that are fascinating and that I wouldn't want to miss." (Interview 4)

Participation in projects was further regarded as a valuable opportunity to establish connections with other actors, both from science and the region, and facilitate the exchange of ideas on specific issues. This was seen as a considerable benefit.

There was a mutual agreement that project outputs and results need to be fed back to practice both by researchers and other actors.

"And how could these project results be fed back to the farmers in such a way that they can make use of them?" (Interview 9)

The participants subsequently proposed a variety of suggestions regarding the processing and dissemination of research results for regional actors. Firstly, the necessity for straightforward summaries of research projects was emphasized, with a particular focus on the dissemination of results for subsequent practical implementation within the region. It is proposed that this dissemination could take the form of concise executive summaries (maximum 1 page), posters, infographics, maps, or related formats. Furthermore, it was anticipated that research projects would yield best practice examples from the Eisenwurzen region, which could then be disseminated to other areas of the region.

In relation to the implementation of research outcomes, stakeholders have indicated that this step is frequently absent for a variety of reasons. These include projects not being designed to incorporate an implementation phase, the funding scheme not encompassing implementation measures, insufficient time during the project, or the inability to implement a planned follow-up project, among other factors.

Also, the necessity for reliable data as a basis for decision-making was expressed, for example, in relation to climate change adaptation measures in the region.

"(...) The XX project, for example, to be specific, could provide a sound, scientific basis for decision-making. Should we now build a large retention dam to store water for agricultural land and at the same time mitigate flooding, or are there other options that would solve the problem much better? In other words, laying the basic foundations is, for me, the core benefit." (Interview 11)

"(...) where I think to myself, okay, if I know there is a platform that provides facts or perhaps best practice examples for ecological gardening in the Almtal valley, for example, where you have already seen, okay, you can implement this and that and that and you need this and that to do so, and you can also say, hey, take a look there, there's already, there's already empirical data, take a look at that" (Interview 12)

Exchange within the LTSE platform

For stakeholders, the platform has the potential to facilitate cooperation and exchange between science and the region, thereby offering a valuable resource for knowledge transfer and collaboration.

At present, this is regarded as being in a weak position, particularly since only limited financial resources are available for platform management and coordination. The majority of activities are dependent on time-limited funding projects, which results in the aforementioned situation whereby science-practice communication ceases after the

conclusion of a project. Furthermore, there is a lack of resources available for the integration of regional stakeholders into the process of developing new research proposals.

“And I think that’s something you really need to focus on. It often seems to me that people don’t ask enough questions before they start researching, like, what do you actually want, how can I help you?” (Interview 10)

A further challenge is encountered by the size of the platform and the fact that it spans three Austrian federal states (Upper Austria, Lower Austria, and Styria) which is inhibiting collaboration.

In order to develop a good and supportive platform structure, the stakeholders consider several points to be important. These include the establishment of a distinct profile or identity for the platform, the establishment of common goals that are also supported by regional stakeholders, and the allocation of a sufficient budget for platform management.

“We were simply the link there in the regions. But otherwise, we didn’t do anything extra. (...) But yes, it does need resources, and I’m also in favor of that, and there needs to be compensation for it, because otherwise it won’t work.” (Interview 2)

2.3.1 Workshop with regional developers

Relationship and collaboration between science and practice

During the workshop, 16 participants emphasized the importance of fostering mutual interactions between scientific and practical domains, underscoring the necessity for reciprocal engagement from both sides. It was highlighted that regional development is both interested in and reliant upon research outcomes for the successful implementation of its projects and activities. Once more, the necessity for dedicated funding to facilitate such projects was deliberated, and a call for a collective endeavor to identify such funding was made. Two proposals were advanced: firstly, the allocation of additional funding with a view to integrating research activities into regional development processes, and secondly, the establishment of small-scale funding opportunities that would facilitate the swift and straightforward implementation of research results within the region.

Benefits and impact in the region

The regional developers agreed that the LTSER platform Eisenwurzen could increase its regional impact by acting as a central coordination hub connecting stakeholders from different sectors and disciplines. It could provide active and transparent support to stakeholders. To strengthen collaboration, the platform could facilitate joint projects and coordinate funding submissions. This could be complemented by a region-specific marketplace to enable efficient project initiation, matchmaking between needs and expertise, and consortium building [R3].

Research outputs could be effectively fed back to regional practitioners by making projects and results highly visible through an interactive project map as the central tool. This could be complemented by a curated database that consolidates best practices, relevant expertise, and ongoing projects. The importance of communicating research results in an understandable manner was emphasized once again.

Another potential benefit identified by the workshop participants was the possibility of gaining access to international LTER networks. This would enable cooperation with other regions and the opportunity to learn from international best practice.

Exchange within the LTSEER platform

In order to facilitate exchange and collaboration, the platform should operate as a regional hub with clear governance and a sustained presence. It should facilitate regular, topic- and results-focused exchanges supported by defined contact points and responsibilities, transparent handover processes during personnel changes and a strong regional presence, with regional development integrated into its activities. The platform should actively involve motivated multipliers and strategic partners, deliberately engage with different sectors (e.g. tourism and agriculture) and leverage and connect existing micro-networks in order to avoid duplication and amplify impact. Ongoing collaboration could be structured by setting up a dedicated working group, possibly comprising the workshop participants, and scheduling follow-up workshops to ensure continuity and progress. The platform's identity should be developed through a participatory process that connects research with the regional population. This involves sharpening the platform's profile and systematically involving multipliers to co-define priorities.

2.4 Defining Necessary Informational Input

The stakeholders expressed the following needs for research results and data that would inform decision-making processes concerning land use and regional development in the context of climate change and adaptation strategies.

Hydroclimate risk and preparedness

- Data on warming-induced evapotranspiration, soil/forest drying, groundwater recharge trends, and the frequency/severity of extreme rainfall
- Integrated hazard and adaptation planning inputs (flood/drought risk maps, retention and infiltration options)
- Specific regional hydrological data and hydroclimatic models

Regional scenarios for land-use and climate change

- Scenario outputs based on simulation models showing how land use intensity and patterns will change under different socio-economic and biophysical assumptions.
- Simulation tools developed in collaboration with regional stakeholders and decision-makers, which can be used interactively in various settings for decision-making, learning, and communication purposes.

Applied climate research and local problem-solving

- Co-produce research with local actors (agriculture, forestry, municipalities).
- Co-development of research questions from regional actors with research partners; documentation of outcomes usable by practitioners and policymakers.
- A current exemplary project monitors parasites and nuisance insects on alpine pastures (prevalence, seasonal dynamics, long-term trends), develops forecasts, and evidence-based management recommendations for alpine farmers

Ecosystem services accounting and certification

- Develop regionally relevant metrics and certification schemes for ecosystem services and biodiversity with a special focus on small-scale mountain farming.

Land-use and nature protection

- Protected area visitation and tourism carrying capacity
- Visitor monitoring data and spatial use patterns to identify ecological thresholds and trigger management actions.
- Studies on acceptable use, route compliance, and impacts; tourism carrying capacity assessments for park and municipalities.

2.5 Defining the Output

The overall objective of the SDL is to further develop the integrated socio-ecological land use model SECLAND, developed by the Institute of Social Ecology (BOKU), in order to analyse how political, economic, social and cultural changes over time affect land use decisions in the Eisenwurzen region. The SECLAND model has been developed in a series of research projects and mainly applied to the Eisenwurzen region. The model provides spatially explicit land use maps for the year 2050 under different scenario assumptions regarding socio-economic, political and climate change.

With this SDL we want to gain (1) a better understanding of the complex interactions between governance structures, land user decision making and the ecosystems in the region and (2) initiate a shift towards nature-based solutions in the management of agricultural and forestry lands.

The SECLAND model is an agent-based model that simulates individual land users in a specific region and their decision-making processes with regard to land use intensity. This bottom-up modelling approach allows simulations based on quantitative input data (e.g. IACS data) and qualitative data based on interviews and workshops to represent land use decisions under different scenario assumptions. The aim is to gain an in-depth understanding of the linkages between political and economic conditions to individual land users, who represent a social unit that takes different positions in different contexts depending on biophysical conditions, demographics, economic needs, values, family situations, etc.

The existing scientific model SECLAND will be redesigned as an inter- and transdisciplinary communication and analysis tool. The participatory modelling approach will be applied with a focus on how to design the interface of the model to be used as an interactive tool for different stakeholder groups. The co-creation process will be based on individual and group discussions with different stakeholder representatives in order to explore the following two aspects: (1) which elements of the framework conditions as well as intrinsic factors (e.g. subsidies, prices, probability of farm succession, etc.) should be displayed on the interface as sliders, so that they can be changed interactively by practitioners, and (2) which parameters should be displayed on the interface as graphs for example, so that one

can see how changes in the framework conditions affect parameters of the socio-ecological system (e.g. land use distribution, average income in agriculture, average workload in agriculture, etc.).

Networking and relationship building are essential for establishing a continuous exchange of information and long-term cooperation between regional stakeholders and researchers. Both sides are responsible for this, and specific tools can support it, such as a project map, a database of projects and results, and co-created tools, such as the land use decision-making model. Creating a dedicated project map, systematically entering projects and ensuring open access – especially for key multipliers – can enable targeted dissemination, facilitate knowledge transfer and support evidence-based practice in the region.

Actors value this exchange and the opportunities it provides to participate in knowledge production with regard to regional research results and international exchange via the LTER network. With regard to knowledge communication, it was emphasised that outputs should be clear and easy to understand. These could be short, practical, application-oriented summaries, infographics, posters, maps or other engaging, creative formats, for example. The regional group of the LTSE platform will continue to collaborate on these tasks. Firstly, a comprehensive database of all research projects in the region will be made available. Furthermore, a simple tool for sharing ideas and developing project partnerships will be developed and made available. The regional group will coordinate further workshops with regional developers to continue networking and developing a shared identity for the LTSE platform.

3 Evaluation of Adaptation and Mitigation Actions to Drought, SDL#2 (Messara–Asterousia, Crete)

3.1 Stakeholder Mapping

In 2016, as part of a European Economic Area funded project titled “INNOVATIVE WATER RESOURCE MANAGEMENT METHODOLOGIES FOR CLIMATE CHANGE ADAPTATION AND GOVERNANCE OF THE REGION OF CRETE – AQUAMAN”, the Technical University of Crete conducted a comprehensive stakeholder mapping of diverse perspectives and values and identification of conflicting objectives for the Region of Crete [R4]. The Deliverable outlined the stakeholders involved and the full consultation process undertaken for developing the Management Plan of the Water District of Crete. It describes the stakeholder concept and analysis methodology, the institutional framework guiding the consultation, the steps followed during the process, and the resulting stakeholder analysis, outcomes, and mapped viewpoints.

A complete list of stakeholders identified in the Nikolaidis et al. [R4] study is presented in Appendix BA. At the National Government level there were identified 42 Ministers and General Secretaries. In addition, there are 2 Professional Chambers, the National Water Council, 19 Governmental and Non-Governmental Organization, and 3 Associations (ie PASEGES) for a total of 72 stakeholders. At the Regional Level the stakeholders were 10 from the Decentralized Administration of Crete, 18 from the Region of Crete, 16 Members of Parliament, 24 Municipalities, 11 Municipal water and Sewage Enterprises, 39 Local Land Reclamation Organizations, the Heraklion Port Authority, 4 Public Legal Entities – (Port Funds), the General Chemical State Lab, 16 Universities/Institutes/Research Centers, 5 Municipal Enterprises (e.g., OAK), 5 Chambers (e.g., TEE/TAK) and 1 Managing Authority (EYDE – BOAK – Aposelemis) for a total of 283 (Figure 2). The stakeholders that participated in the consultation process were 55 and a list is presented in Appendix B.

The list of stakeholders identified in the Nikolaidis et al. [R4] study is comprehensive and appropriate to be applied for stakeholder engagement at the present day. From this list, the stakeholders to be involved in SDL#2 were selected to include farmers, agronomists, water utilities, irrigation organizations that are related to the Messara and Asterousia Mountains area.

The co-design of the selection of local stakeholders was conducted with representatives from the Region of Crete and the Decentralized Administration of Crete. The following directorates participated in the selection: Sustainable Development Division, Water Directory, Forestry Directorate). The following local and regional stakeholders were

identified as appropriate to participate in the co-design of the strategic plan to address desertification in the Messara-Asterousia Mountains area of Crete.

- Municipalities of Faistos, Gortyna and municipal unit of Asterousia
- Water and Sewerage Company of Faistos
- Local Organizations of Land Improvements (TOEV Messara (Zones A, B and C), Zarou, Gergeris and Vasilikon-Anogion)
- UNESCO – Asterousia Biosphere Reserve – Association for the Protection of Asterousia Mountains
- Universities/Institutes/Research Centers of Crete that conduct research in the region (University of Crete, Hellenic Mediterranean University, Technical University of Crete, Museum of Natural History of Crete, Hellenic Agricultural Organization, Hellenic Center for Marine Research)
- Development Agency of Heraklion
- Development Organization of Crete
- Local cooperatives
- Local agronomists
- WWF-Crete

Figure 2. National and Regional Stakeholder Mapping for SDL#2.

3.2 Co-Design Service Lab with Region

The service under development will support the region in several keyways: by synthesizing existing scientific and local knowledge, by identifying the most appropriate methods for engaging agricultural stakeholders, and by facilitating a participatory co-design process. It aims to co-design a comprehensive program of measures that will address the impacts of climate change. It will bring together policymakers, technical experts, and local actors, particularly farmers and shepherds, to jointly shape practical, grounded, and effective adaptation actions. Through structured dialogue, workshops, and field-level interactions, the service will help ensure that the resulting program of measures reflects both regional policy priorities and the needs of stakeholders [R1]. Ultimately, the aim is to produce nature-based solutions that are not only technically sound, but also feasible, accepted by local practitioners, and straightforward to implement.

The methodological approach implemented has three phases (Figure 3) and has been presented in detail in IRISCC deliverable D2.1. In the first phase, co-design engagement efforts are initiated with the regional government of Crete, and a framework is developed addressing soil degradation and desertification in the Messara and Asterousia regions of Crete. In collaboration with the regional government, the objective of action is defined, and stakeholders are identified. The co-design engagement approach is established, and all relevant knowledge input is identified. In the second phase, a baseline narrative is created from the existing knowledge and data collected and a science proposition is developed. The objective of the science proposition is to develop a list of alternatives that can be used alone or in combination to alleviate the impacts of desertification. These solutions address all the aspects of the WEF NEXUS aiming for security of resources while maintaining and enhancing ecosystem sustainability. These solutions will be presented to stakeholders to assess their viability, what roadblocks are preventing their implementation, which ones are most appropriate for the region and to assess if the community has the capacity to implement these solutions [R5]. Based on the science proposition, stakeholders are asked to set priorities which will be evaluated based on similarities and to select alternative solutions taking into account conflicts in perceptions. Certain scenarios will be run; this will be done through multi-criteria analysis and ranking. The co-design strategy is modified and improved to the stakeholder needs and perceptions and the selection of alternatives/solutions is designated. Accordingly, a roadmap for implementation is created, including measures in legislation and funding mechanisms. The third phase concerns scaling up the knowledge and includes two parts: the education and training phase and communication and dissemination phase. A communication strategy will be launched through social media and a webpage and training workshops [R5].

The methodologies in development will draw on the experience of stakeholder engagement of EnviFriendly Innovations and the eLTER RI. Together, their approaches aim to create a generalized, transferable methodology that can be applied at the regional level to assess environmental challenges and support the translation of scientific knowledge into practical solutions [R6].

Figure 3. Co-design engagement of SDL #2 in Crete.

The overarching goal is to bridge the gap between research, policy, and enabling regions to address both global and local socio-ecological challenges more effectively. Within this framework, eLTER RI will act as a catalyst for change by providing long-term ecological data, interdisciplinary expertise, and transnational research support. Its role is not only to inform evidence-based decision-making but also to empower regions to implement innovative, sustainable strategies shaped by scientific understanding [R7].

The regions involved—such as Asterousia, designated as a UNESCO site World Network of Biosphere Reserves and part of “Man and the Biosphere Program”—offer ideal contexts for testing and refining this methodology. Their unique ecological characteristics, cultural landscapes, and existing environmental pressures make them valuable for developing solutions that can be scaled, replicated, and adapted across Europe and beyond.

The developers of the service, program of measures are EnviFriendly Innovations and the regional Government of Crete. Data for the assessment will come primarily from the eLTER RI local observatory, the Region of Crete, the Technical University of Crete, and ELSTAT, each providing ecological, sociological, economical, and statistical information that together form the knowledge base. The stakeholder landscape spans both high-level and local actors (Table 1). At the upper level, the regional government of Crete, major research institutions and the eLTER RI coordination bodies provide policy direction, technical oversight, and scientific data. At the local level, municipalities, farmers and shepherds, local water management bodies, NGOs, community groups, and UNESCO-related actors in Asterousia contribute practical knowledge, place-based experience, and direct involvement in implementation.

Local and regional actors will be engaged throughout the process to ensure data accuracy, policy alignment, and social acceptance while contributing to practical insights essential for co-designing feasible and locally appropriate measures [R8].

Table 1. Summary of stakeholders, and their role in the project.

Level	Stakeholders	Role / Function
High-Level Stakeholders	Region of Crete	Provide strategic direction, policy guidance, and overall governance.
Data Providers Layer	eLTER Local Observatory; Region of Crete Data; TUC Data; ELSTAT	Supply scientific, regional, and statistical data used to generate knowledge and inform action.
Local Stakeholders	Municipalities; Farmers & Shepherds; Local Water Bodies; NGOs / Local Communities; UNESCO Asterousia Association, Research Institutions	Participate in local implementation, co-design of measures, and practical adaptation actions.

3.3 User Requirements and Needs

The regional government requires support in designing a comprehensive strategic plan to address and mitigate the progressing desertification in the area. This includes evidence-based guidance on long-term land management, water governance, and ecosystem restoration. At the same time, farmers, agronomists, and agricultural associations are seeking practical and actionable solutions that can be implemented easily. Their needs extend to improved land-use practices, restoration and maintenance of soil ecosystem services, adoption of efficient irrigation methods, and whole system approaches to sustainable water and soil management. Together, these groups require both strategic direction and operational tools against desertification and ensure the long-term productivity and sustainability of the region's landscapes.

The Messara region of Crete faces a series of interconnected challenges that involve agriculture, land degradation, water management, and social governance. Agricultural development is under increasing pressure due to high irrigation water demands that strain groundwater reserves, a decline in food production affecting the local economy, persistent supply-chain and marketing barriers, and a widespread dependence on CAP subsidies that often encourage unsustainable practices and diminishes social trust [R4]. At the same time, the region is experiencing significant land degradation and biodiversity loss, evident in declining soil fertility and carbon levels, reduced species richness, accelerated soil erosion from unsustainable land management, and growing impacts on both groundwater and surface water, including nitrate and organic pollution as well as lowered water tables. Social tensions add an additional layer of complexity, particularly conflicts between livestock breeders and farmers across the Messara plain, which hinder coordinated management efforts [R4, R7].

Across the wider Crete Water District, stakeholders identify water pollution from fertilizers, pesticides, and insecticides as the most urgent issue, followed by concerns about the availability and quality of drinking water. Industrial and livestock-related pollution, groundwater overexploitation, urban waste, insufficient control of water abstraction, and the availability of irrigation water also rank highly, while the lowest-priority concern relates to projects that alter natural characteristics, such as dams or small hydropower installations. Current stakeholder perceptions also highlight ongoing challenges with wastewater treatment and irrigation infrastructure, including multiple sludge lagoon and lagoon reconstruction projects, the construction or improvement of wastewater treatment plants in several municipalities, and investments in water supply systems such as remote-control operation networks, a proposed desalination unit with a planned capacity of 30,000 m³, and preliminary studies for two dams intended to support irrigation. Together, these issues illustrate a region where environmental pressures, water scarcity, infrastructure needs, and social dynamics converge, creating an urgent need for coordinated, sustainable, and science-informed management strategies. [R4]

The Asterousia Mountains face significant environmental pressures, including land degradation and biodiversity loss driven by overgrazing and increasing flock sizes, which reduce vegetation cover and intensify soil erosion and desertification risks [R9]. Intensive fodder use further diminishes plant diversity, while sensitive ecosystems—such as riparian

zones, sand dunes, Mediterranean pine forests, and wetlands—are damaged by unsustainable grazing practices [R10]. The spread of invasive alien species adds further pressure to native habitats [R10]. Socioeconomic challenges compound these issues, with the region experiencing notable demographic decline and an aging population, having lost around 30% of its residents between 1961 and 2011 [R7]. Educational attainment remains low, with nearly 70% of residents having completed only primary education or less [R9]. Agricultural profitability is diminishing due to rising feed prices, declining milk prices, and stricter subsidy regulations, while dependence on CAP subsidies encourages unsustainable practices and undermines social trust [R9]. Tourism adds additional pressure, as ecotourism lacks coordinated planning to prevent environmental degradation [R10]. Social capital and governance challenges further obstruct sustainable development: bridging social capital has weakened since the 1980s, reducing cooperation among farmers, stockbreeders, and institutions, while bonding social capital remains strong but contributes to low wider social trust [R10]. Conflicts between livestock breeders and farmers persist in the Messara plain, alongside broader distrust toward institutions and resistance to modernization or sustainable grazing policies [R10]. Governance structures remain weak, limiting the region’s capacity to address these interconnected challenges effectively [R11].

Co-design sessions and collaborative activities

Multiple co-design sessions and collaborative activities have taken place with the Region of Crete. A meeting with key stakeholders from the Region of Crete took place on December 4, 2024 discussing the objective of action of the SDL, the engagement approach and the key stakeholders that would be involved in the SDL.

On August 18th, 2025, a meeting took place with the Region of Crete to carry out a baseline study for the Asterousia Mountains that will reinforce and endorse an Operational Plan “*Protection and Promotion with Sustainability Principles for the Asterousia Mountains.*” This study will be presented to stakeholders for suggestions and with the assistance of EnviFriendly Innovations will pursue implementation.

EnviFriendly Innovations founding members took soil samples from the Kapetaniana village of Asterousia Mountains and convened with high-ranking members of the Region of Crete concerning stakeholder engagement strategy. Furthermore, EnviFriendly Innovations participated at the Hybrid Asterousia University 2025 conference titled ‘Natural & Cultural Heritage in Biosphere Reserves and Other Designated Areas in the Mediterranean,’ organized by the Mediterranean Information Office for Environment, Culture, and Sustainable Development (MIO-ECSDE) and the UNESCO Regional Office for Science and Culture in Europe, with the contribution of the Region of Crete, the Heraklion Development Agency, and the Local Management Committee of Asterousia, on October 30th, 2025, an event which enhanced the engagement with stakeholders and fostered a setting of collaboration.

There are several notable knowledge and data gaps affecting effective environmental and water management in the region. There is an urgent need for strategic thinking, WEF Nexus analysis in each region, co-design and selection of solutions with local stakeholders, as well as demonstrations pilots to ensure widespread acceptance of adapted alternatives.

3.4 Defining Necessary Informational Input

Existing studies, models and tools will be utilized to synthesize the baseline conditions of the study areas regarding the status of desertification and identify appropriate actions to address climate change impacts and reverse the risk of desertification. The data that are required to map the WEF Nexus are the following:

Water supply and demand

- Karst SWAT model simulations for available water – Forty year-long simulations (1980–2020) have been performed using the Crete-SWAT model [R11] for 354 subbasins for the island of Crete. The simulation was part of the analysis to determine the available water in each subbasin and contribute to the River Basin Management Plan for the Region of Crete. Messara river basin and several subbasins of Asterousia Mountains were included in the simulations. Time series of rainfall and meteorological data and simulated hydrologic flows are available for the determination of the water budget in each subbasin.
- Water supply and demand data and analysis – As part of the supporting studies of the River Basin Management Plan of Crete, an analysis of the water supply and demand has been conducted. These data will be used for the analysis of water shortages and the evaluation of alternatives to achieve water security.
- Climate change projections – The EEA AQUAMAN study has conducted climate change simulations using 11 climate projections with different combinations of global and regional climate models [R1]. The results will be used to determine the decreases in available water due to climate change and the reliability of the proposed solutions to mitigate the impacts of climate change.

Energy supply and demand

- Energy demand for irrigation – The Region of Crete has conducted a study to determine the energy demand for irrigation of 26 Local Irrigation Organizations of Crete and conducted the design and techno-economic analysis the energy to be supplied by solar (photovoltaics) renewable energy. The results of this study will be used in the assessment of the WEF Nexus.

Food production

- Soil fertility analysis and risk assessments – Soil data from the Messara valley will be used to assess the fertility of the soil and desertification risk assessment studies from the literature will be used to determine the current status of soil.
- Soil analysis – Additional soil sampling and analysis will be conducted to ensure the assessed status from the literature.
- Food production – Statistical data from the ELSTAT on food production for the region will be used to relate soil fertility and food production.
- Pilot demonstration studies on soil fertility – Demonstration studies on soil fertility will be collected and assessed as viable alternatives to reverse desertification and lower the climate change vulnerability of the soils.

Environmental status

- Groundwater and surface water assessments – Historical data and studies on the quality of surface and groundwater will be used in the assessment of the baseline conditions.
- Ecological quality – Analysis of ecological status of surface and groundwater from the River Basin Management Plan will also be used to determine the baseline conditions.
- European projects in the region – Literature review of EU funded projects on desertification of Crete will be conducted for the assessment.

Regional Strategic Plans

The Region of Crete has conducted the following studies that relate to the WEFE Nexus analysis:

- Plan for the Adaptation to Climate Change in the Region of Crete
- Action Plan for Addressing Drought–Water Shortages in the Region of Crete
- River Basin Management Plan
- Flood Risk Management Plan

These studies have proposed measures to alleviate the impacts of climate change, minimize the risk of floods and droughts and improve the ecological status of surface and groundwaters. These measures will be considered in our analysis and in the development of the baseline conditions for the region. An input database was created as part of WP5.1 to collect the models and methods each SDL is using for data collection.

3.5 Defining the Output

The SDL#2 will produce a comprehensive strategic plan that provides a clear vision, defines strategic goals, and proposes a co-designed program of measures developed collaboratively with farmers and local stakeholders. This strategic plan will focus on optimizing the WEFE Nexus goals—ensuring water, energy, and food security—while simultaneously improving environmental conditions across the region. A priority is addressing the increasing risk of desertification, which is driven not only by climate change but also by long-standing local land-use and agricultural practices. The proposed measures will draw from existing scientific knowledge and successful practices already implemented in Crete as well as in other regions with comparable environmental challenges.

The expected outcomes include shifts in local agro-ecological practices, particularly in irrigation management and soil restoration, along with adjustments to agricultural policies—such as CAP incentives—that encourage long-term sustainability. These changes will open pathways for new business and development opportunities that align with sustainable water and soil management. Ultimately, all stakeholders—including farmers, local communities, and regional authorities—stand to gain from improved water governance, enhanced soil and ecosystem health, and more sustainable agricultural production systems that reinforce both environmental quality and economic viability.

The socio-ecological methodology developed in the EcoFuture-PRIMA project [R5] will be adapted to articulate an Agricultural Transformation Strategy for the region. The purpose

of that strategy is not to promote isolated interventions but to propose a coherent transformation pathway. To this end, the robust set of measures is synthesised into an Agricultural Transformation Strategy which represents a strategic shift in the way agricultural development, resource management and ecosystem stewardship are conceived and implemented in MessaraValley. Rather than intensifying existing practices through increased inputs and centralised infrastructure, the proposed is based on an integrated, regenerative and resource-conscious paradigm aligned with the WEFE nexus.

Capacity training through workshops, webinars will take place after the action plan has been developed. Community Capacity assessment will be conducted to identify the capacity of the community to implement the solutions and the actions that we need to take to facilitate the process. Also, by co-designing the actions with the regional government, it creates capacity building for the region.

4 Synthesis and Conclusions

This report presents the user requirements of the regional scale SDLs of the IRISCC Project. Across both SDLs, a number of shared findings emerge that highlight the central role of stakeholder-driven, region-based approaches for addressing complex socio-ecological challenges. Both cases demonstrate that multiple stakeholder groups are clearly concerned with land-use and climate adaptation challenges where environmental pressures, governance structures, and socio-economic dynamics intersect. Whether in the Eisenwurzen region or the Messara-Asterousia area of Crete, effective responses require coordinated action across agriculture, forestry, water management, conservation, regional development, and policy domains.

Stakeholders in both regions consistently emphasized the importance of integrating scientific knowledge with local and experiential knowledge. Long-term data, models, and analytical tools—such as those provided by eLTER RI—are seen as essential foundations for evidence-based decision-making. However, their value has the potential to be implemented only when translated into accessible, context-specific, and actionable formats that align with regional priorities and capacities which can be achieved only with extensive engagement throughout all levels of implementation of the project. Both SDL's reveal that perceived benefits and tangible regional impact are decisive for sustained stakeholder engagement. While benefits may range from awareness raising and learning to concrete implementation support, the absence of measurable feedback, follow-up, or implementation pathways risks disengagement. Networking and exchange, particularly at the interface between science, policy, and practice, were consistently identified as key added values of the Service Design Lab approach.

The stakeholder engagement methods applied across both Labs illustrate the strengths and challenges of participatory co-design in regional contexts. Stakeholder mapping and social system analysis proved essential for identifying key actors, intermediaries, and communication pathways, allowing for a more strategic and inclusive engagement process. In both cases, regional development actors play a critical role in bridging science and practice. Open Science and FAIR Data principles the refer to citizen science – participatory research guidelines (best practices) will be followed throughout the implementation.

Interviews and workshops enabled in-depth insights into stakeholder needs, expectations, and past experiences with research collaboration. A recurring theme was the need for collaboration on equal terms, where different forms of knowledge are recognized and valued. One-sided interactions, whether stakeholders acting merely as data providers or scientists perceived solely as technical service providers, were seen as limiting the transformative potential of collaboration.

Time constraints, resource limitations, and unequal compensation structures remain major barriers to participation, particularly for farmers and land users. Informed facilitation, careful timing, and early but meaningful involvement of stakeholders were identified as essential conditions for effective participation. Importantly, both SDL's highlight that

participatory processes must extend beyond individual project lifecycles to avoid fragmentation and loss of trust.

Based on the findings from both SDL's, several recommendations can be derived for effective service implementation and scaling up. First, SDLs should be embedded within a stable platform structure that ensures continuity beyond individual projects. Dedicated resources for coordination, communication, and stakeholder engagement are essential to maintain long-term exchange and collaboration.

Second, services should prioritize the development of clear, user-oriented outputs, such as project maps, curated databases of results and best practices, concise summaries, and visual tools. These instruments support knowledge transfer, enhance transparency, and enable stakeholders to integrate scientific insights into decision-making and practice.

Third, implementation-oriented components, including pilot actions, demonstration projects, and small-scale funding mechanisms, are critical to bridge the gap between research and practice. Dissemination should not focus solely on replication, but on adaptability; methodologies and tools must be flexible enough to respond to diverse regional contexts, governance settings, and stakeholder capacities.

Finally, leveraging transnational networks such as eLTER RI can amplify impact by facilitating cross-regional learning, comparative analysis, and the transfer of successful approaches between regions facing similar challenges.

Future engagement should focus on consolidating the SDL approach as a continuous process rather than a project-based intervention. This includes establishing dedicated working groups, follow-up workshops, and regular exchange formats that bring together researchers, regional developers, policymakers, and practitioners.

Further integration of stakeholders into the early stages of research agenda setting and proposal development would strengthen relevance and ownership. At the same time, systematic monitoring of impacts—both tangible and intangible—would help make benefits more visible and support learning across regions.

In both regions, the next steps involve moving from co-design to implementation and capacity building. This includes training and education activities, support for local governance and coordination structures, and the co-development of roadmaps that align scientific evidence with policy instruments and funding mechanisms. By doing so, SDLs can evolve into durable interfaces between science, policy, and practice, supporting transformative and regionally grounded responses to climate change and land-use challenges.

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R10	<p>Kosmas, C., Karamesouti, M., Kounalaki, K., Detsis, V., Vassiliou, P., and Salvati, L. (2016). Land degradation and long-term changes in agro-pastoral systems: an empirical analysis of ecological resilience in Asteroussia – Crete (Greece). <i>Catena</i>, 147, 196–204. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2016.07.018</p>
R11	<p>Malagò, A., Efstathiou, D., Bouraoui, F., Nikolaidis, N. P., Franchini, M., Bidoglio, G., & Kritsotakis, M. (2016). Regional scale hydrologic modeling of a karst-dominant geomorphology: The case study of the island of Crete. <i>Journal of Hydrology</i>, 540, 64–81. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2016.05.061</p>

Appendix A – Interview Guideline – Actor interviews LTSER platform (Eisenwurzen)

Target group: actors from science and practice, who are/were active in the LTSER platform in different roles: coordination of platform and/or projects, participating in projects connected to the platform

Introductory question

Our discussion today is about the involvement of various actors in research in the Eisenwurzen LTSER platform (especially in projects led by or involving research institutions). By actors, I mean both scientists and people from the field who were and are involved in research projects – so when I talk about ‘projects’ in this interview, I am referring to these research projects.

To begin with, I am interested in your personal history with the LTSER Platform Eisenwurzen: When and how did you become involved in the LTSER Platform Eisenwurzen? What was the motivation behind it? Who were the people you were in contact with at the time, who did you work with, what topics were important at the beginning?

A) Thematic link to your own field of activity

- Which topics are generally important in your field of work?
- Which of these topics do you link to the LTSER platform?
- How have the thematic areas with which you engage with the platform changed over time? Which topics are constantly relevant?
- Which topics have you been able to contribute to the platform yourself?
- When you think of past projects in which you were involved: Can you give examples that have brought you concrete benefits in your work? What were these benefits (new ideas, economic benefits, new contacts, etc.)?
- Which topics do you think are not addressed enough within the platform?

B) Network

The LTSER platform consists of a network of institutions/organisations and individuals. I would like to talk to you about this in the next block of questions.

- Which people do you have regular/frequent contact with in connection with the LTSER Platform?
- Which people (organisations) have you worked with in your last projects on the platform?

- Which people do you think have a significant influence on the organisation of activities on the platform?
- Do you know people who used to be active on the platform but are no longer?
- Do you know why this is the case?
- How is the LTSER platform perceived in the region? (Is it recognised and if so, by whom?)
- What do you think a platform needs, what elements are important in order to be useful for you?
- What do you expect from being part of a platform and what would you like to contribute as an actor?

C) Involvement in projects, participation, processes:

For this study, we want to know more about the involvement of affected actors in research projects in order to incorporate their concerns and expertise into the research. This can be done in different ways and to varying degrees. This often takes the form of workshops or focus groups.

- Present a list of projects (LTSER list). Which platform projects have you been involved in so far? Are any projects missing?
- Which of these projects did you perceive as participatory?
- How was participation organised? How was the participation process organised?
- In your opinion, what worked well in the participation process? What worked not so well? Methods, venues, participating actors from the region (was anyone missing?); Conflict resolution, etc.
- Have there been changes in the participation process over time?
 - More or less participation? Other methods?
 - Over time, across the various projects you have been involved in
 - Possible question: Within individual projects (if this is possible to answer)
- How was communication between the project leaders and the different actors/actor types/groups (including the scientists)?
 - Which actor groups are in your view
 - strongly involved?
 - weakly involved?
 - underrepresented?

In which subject areas?

- In general
 - Can you give examples of projects/topics?
 - How important is it for you to network and exchange ideas with other actors in participation processes? (With whom? For what purposes? What benefits do you gain/have you already gained from this?)

D) Results/impact

This block of questions is about the results of the research projects in the LTSER platform and their impact for the region and for practice.

- How important is it to you that the results of the projects also have an impact in practice?
- Which results from the projects in which you were involved have had an impact in the region in your view? (ask for specific examples if necessary)
- Which results could you usefully implement in your area of activity? And if so, how?
Ask about different areas:
 - Ecological effects,
 - sustainable regional development, possibly economic development,
 - Networking of actors within the region
 - Networking of actors beyond the region
- Which results were interesting?
- In what form would you like to receive the results?

Appendix B – Stakeholder Mapping

The Stakeholder at the **National Level** identified and invited to the public consultation on the Management Plan of the Water District of Crete (Nikolaidis et al., 2016) were the following:

- 42 Ministries, Ministry Directorates, Ministers and General Secretaries
- 1 National Water Council (Members of the National Water Council)
- 8 Governmental and Non-Governmental Organizations (EYDAP, ELSTAT, etc.)
- 3 Associations (PASEGES, KEDE, EDEYA)
- 2 Chambers of Commerce (TEE, GEOTEE)
- 3 Various Entities (SEGM, SEV, ELANET)
- 2 Universities/Institutes/Research Centers
- 11 Non-Governmental Organizations (WWF, Arcturos, MedSOS Network, etc.)

The Stakeholder at the **Regional** Level identified and invited to the public consultation on the Management Plan of the Water District of Crete were the following:

- 10 agencies of the Decentralized Administration of Crete (Forestry Directorates, etc.)
- 18 agencies of the Region of Crete
- 16 Members of Parliament
- 24 Municipalities
- 11 Municipal Enterprises (Water and Sewerage Companies)
- 39 Local Organizations of Land Improvements (TOEBs)
- 1 Organization – S.A. (Heraklion Port Authority)
- 4 Legal Entities of Public Law (Port Funds)
- 1 Ministry Agency (General Chemistry)
- 16 Universities/Institutes/Research Centers
- 5 Municipal Enterprises (OAK, etc.)
- 5 Chambers (TEE/TAK, etc.)
- 1 Managing Authority (EYEDE – BOAK – Aposelemi)
- 15 Associations – Clubs (Heraklion Hoteliers Association, etc.)
- 4 Federations (federations of professional artisans and merchants)
- 1 Inter-municipal enterprise (DEDISA)
- 1 Municipal S.A. (FOSDA)
- 14 Cooperatives (Unions of agricultural cooperatives, etc.)
- 16 Non-Governmental Organizations (Ecological Groups, etc.)
- 8 TV Stations (Crete TV, etc.)
- 26 Newspapers (Chaniotika Nea, etc.)
- 35 Radio Stations (Radio Crete, etc.)
- 1 Port Authorities (Chania, Heraklion, etc.)

A total of 355 stakeholders were invited, 72 from the national level and 283 from the regional level. **Agencies that participated in the consultation** were the following:

The Region of Crete:

- Regional Units (RU): Lasithi, Heraklion, Rethymno, and Chania,
- General Directorates of Development Planning, Environment, and Infrastructure: RU Lasithi, RU Rethymno,
- Directorates of Technical Works: RU Lasithi, RU Rethymno
- Department of Environmental Structures,
- Departments of Environment & Water Management: RU Lasithi, RU Chania
- Environmental Directorate: Municipality of Faistos, Heraklion Prefecture

Decentralized Administration of Crete Municipal Enterprises: Water Supply and Sewerage (DEYA): DEYA Agios Nikolaos, DEYA Siteia, DEYA Rethymno, DEYA Heraklion, DEYA Malevizi, DEYA Minoa Pediada of Heraklion Municipality, DEYA Chania, DEYA Northern Axis (DEYABA) of Platanias Municipality, Crete Development Organization (OAK), former OADYK and OANAK

The Municipalities by regional unit: Lasithi: Municipality of Sitia, Municipality of Agios Nikolaos, Municipality of Ierapetra, Heraklion: Municipality of Viannos, Municipality of Minoa Pediada, Rethymno: Municipality of Mylopotamos, Municipality of Anogeia, Municipality of Amari, Municipality of Faistos, Chania: Municipality of Apokoronas, Municipality of Platanias, Municipality of Kissamos, Municipality of Sfakia, Municipality of Gavdos, Municipality of Kantanos-Selino

The Municipal Units, Local Communities, and Settlements: Settlement Gra Lygia of the Municipality of Ierapetra, Community of Christ (also representing the Communities of Males and Metaxochori of the Municipality of Ierapetra), Municipality of Agios Vasileios, Municipal unit of Foinikas of the Municipality of Rethymno, Municipality of Agios Vasileios – Municipal unit of Lappa of the Municipality of Rethymno, Community of Stylos – Apokoronas of the Municipality of Chania

The Local Land Reclamation Organizations (TOEBs): TOEB Ierapetra, TOEB of Kalo Chorio in the Municipality of Agios Nikolaos, TOEB of Chrysoskalitissa in the Municipality of Agios Nikolaos, TOEB Papagiannades of Sitia, TOEB Zakros of the Municipality of Sitia

Universities, Institutes, and Research Centers: Institute of Geological and Mineral Exploration and Studies (IGMEM), Technological Educational Institute of Crete

Public Law Entities: Chania Prefecture Port Fund • Chambers: Technical Chamber (TEE) of Western Crete • Non-Governmental Organization: Protection of Greek Island Wetlands (WWF Greece)

Cooperatives: Union of Agricultural Cooperatives (EAS) of Ierapetra